

Adsorption Hysteresis in Some Swelling Systems

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Studies of sorption-desorption of water vapour on swelling systems may exhibit hysteresis effect. This effect is found to decrease and finally disappear on continuing sorption-desorption cycles^{1'2'3'4}.

Although some data are available^{5'6} for cellophane, there are no such data for Agar and *Plantago ovata* seed husk (*P. ovata*). In this communication, sorption-desorption studies, at 35°, of water vapour on these three systems are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Quartz fiber spring technique^{7'8} has been employed in the present investigations. The study was continued up to 3rd or 4th cycle. The springs used in these experiments had sensitivities of about 40 cm of stretch per gram of load. A cathetometer reading correct to 10⁻³ cm was employed for measuring length and stretch of the springs.

The adsorbents had following specifications : Agar (Harleco. U.S.A.); particle size between 100 and 200 mesh (British standard sieves); moisture content 13.2%; ash content 3.2%; acid insoluble ash 0.48%.

P. ovata seed husk ('Sat Isabgol' Sidhpur, India); seed length 1.0–3.0 mm; seed width 1.0–1.75 mm; boat shaped; white with a pinkish tinge; particle size between 100 and 200 mesh (B.S.S.); moisture content 10.5%; ash content 2.96%.

Cellophane : Commercially available cellophane was kept in contact with distilled water and washed several times to remove glycerine which is usually present in cellophane as plasticiser⁹. The washed cellophane was dried in air and used as strips (6 cm × 4 cm) in the present sorption-desorption studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Complete sorption and desorption isotherms, at 35°, of water vapour on cellophane, Agar and *P. ovata* have shown certain common characteristics. The hysteresis effect initially exhibited disappears on successive sorption-desorption cycles. In case of cellophane and *P. ovata*, the disappearance is in the 2nd cycle while in case of Agar the effect disappears gradually and sorption-desorption isotherms become coincident in the 3rd cycle. The results obtained with *P. ovata* are only presented in figure 1. The weight of water sorbed per 100 g of *P. ovata* is plotted against the vapour pressure of water.

FIG 1

Fig. 1. Sorption-desorption hysteresis of water vapour on *P. ovata* at the 1st, 2nd and 3rd cycles.

The present results may be explained in the light of the 'cavity theory' of hysteresis. During sorption, the adsorbent swells and the cavity walls become elastic whereas during desorption it shrinks and cavities collapse in stages. If all the cavities collapse in the very first cycle of sorption and desorption, there will be no hysteresis in the first cycle itself and the sorption-desorption curves will be coincident. If, on the other hand, the cavities collapse in stages, the disappearance of the loop will not be sudden. The loop decreases gradually in size and finally it disappears. Our results indicate that the tendency of Agar to change is low and cavities tend to decrease in size and shape and collapse slowly as compared with those of *P. ovata* and cellophane.

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